

English as a global international language

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Abstract

English is used as a mother tongue by approximately 400 million people in many countries around the world. Therefore, English is the 3rd most spoken language after Chinese and Spanish. Therefore, worldwide participation in exams such as IELTS is quite high. There is no official definition of “global” or “world” language, but it essentially refers to a language that is learned and spoken internationally, and is characterized not only by the number of its native and second language speakers, but also by its geographical distribution, and its use in international organizations and in diplomatic relations. A global language acts as a “lingua franca”, a common language that enables people from diverse backgrounds and ethnicities to communicate on a more or less equitable basis.

Key words: major, real, vital, significance, priority, visible, reality, domestic, international, viewers, global, solution, specific, obvious, example

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Отрывок

Английский язык используется в качестве родного примерно для 400 миллионов человек во многих странах мира. Таким образом, английский является третьим по распространенности языком после китайского и испанского. Поэтому участие в таких экзаменах, как IELTS, во всем мире довольно велико. Официального определения «глобального» или «мирового» языка не существует, но, по сути, он относится к языку, который изучается и на котором говорят на международном уровне, и характеризуется не только количеством носителей его родного и второго языков, но и географическим расположением. распространение и его использование в международных организациях и в дипломатических отношениях. Глобальный язык действует как «лингва франка», общий язык, который позволяет людям разного происхождения и национальностей общаться на более или менее равноправной основе.

Ключевые слова: главный, реальный, жизненно важный, значимость, приоритет, видимый, реальность, внутренний, международный, зрители, глобальный, решение, конкретный, очевидный, пример.

Are you a polyglot or you speak only one language? I am sure, you must be speaking more than one languages. Then you are a polyglot. A person who can speak more than one language is a polyglot. So, you speak Hindi which is our national language, you speak your regional language and you speak English which is considered as a global language. In this blog we will discuss English as a global language.

What is Global Language?

A global language is one that is spoken and understood by a large number of individuals on a worldwide scale. Furthermore, the English language is the only one in the world that most closely matches this definition. More information on this subject will be provided in the blog on English as a global language.

English as a Global Language:

One may convincingly argue that there is a relationship between linguistic supremacy and cultural power when it comes to languages. Furthermore, a strong power base—whether it is political, economic, or military—is the primary reason that the languages gain popularity.

Languages like French, Latin, German, and other European languages were the sources from which the English language developed. This may be the cause of the ease with which many Europeans pick up the English language. Linguists also debate whether English's ease of use is the primary factor in its success as a universal tongue.

People seem to find it easier to recognize and understand the Latin script of the English language. Additionally, English pronunciation is simpler than that of other languages, such as Turkish or Korean, for instance.

No culture has completely lost all knowledge of the English language or terms as a result of the extensive British colonial conquests. Because of this, no community should find English to be too foreign or weird. As a result, learning English is not a major deal for most individuals because they already have a basic understanding of it.

How English Became a Global Language

By the late 18th century, the British Empire had spread English through its colonies. Commerce, Science & technology, diplomacy etc all contributed to English becoming its first truly global language. Business and English are prime partners, the world is taking globalisation seriously, and having a common language only makes business easier. With top-notch companies establishing their presence in different parts of the world, communication becomes vital. We cannot speak all the languages of the world and we need a common link language to interact with different people of the world.

In Shakespeare's time, the number of English speakers in the world is thought to have been between five and seven million. According to linguist David Crystal, "Between the end of the reign of Elizabeth I (1603) and the beginning of the reign of Elizabeth II (1952), this figure increased almost fiftyfold, to around 250 million" (The Cambridge Encyclopedia of the English Language, 2003). It's a common language used in international business, which makes it a popular second language for many.

How Many Languages Are There?

There are roughly 6,500 languages spoken in the world today. About 2,000 of them have fewer than 1,000 speakers. While the British empire did help spread the language globally it's only the third most commonly spoken language in the world. Mandarin and Spanish are the two most commonly spoken languages on Earth.

From How Many Other Languages Has English Borrowed Words?

English is jokingly referred to as a language thief because of it has incorporated words from over 350 other languages into it. The majority of these "borrowed" words are Latin or from one of the Romance languages.

By Kenneth Beare

How Many People in the World Today Speak English?

Roughly 500 million people in the world are native English speakers. Another 510 million people speak English as a second language, which means that there are more people who speak English along with their native language than there are native English speakers.

In How Many Countries Is English Taught as a Foreign Language?

English is taught as a foreign language in over 100 countries. It's considered the language of business which makes it a popular choice for a second language. English language teachers are often paid very well in countries like China and Dubai.

What Is the Most Widely Used English Word?

"The form OK or okay is probably the most intensively and widely used (and borrowed) word in the history of the language. Its many would-be etymologists have traced it variously to Cockney, French, Finnish, German, Greek, Norwegian, Scots, several African languages, and the Native American language Choctaw, as well as a nu Chartered Management Institute (2014) Managing for diversity. CMI management checklist 152

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